

worm

**Waste in humanitarian Operations:
Reduction and Minimisation**

D10.1. Updated Data Management Plan

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V1.0	Kovács, Gyöngyi (Hanken)	30/04/2025	Final version

LIST OF ACRONYMS

ACRONYM	FULL NAME
CLD	Causal loop diagram
DMP	Data management plan
DoA	Description of action
DPA	Data processing agreement
DPIA	Data protection impact assessment
DPO	Data protection officer
EC	European Commission

EU	European Union
FAIR	Data are findable, accessible, interoperable, and reuseable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation of the EU (2016/679)
HEU	Horizon Europe
HNPW	Humanitarian Networks and Partnerships Weeks
IPR	Intellectual property right(s)
LCA	Life cycle assessment
WORM	Waste in humanitarian Operations: Reduction and Minimisation
WPs	Work Packages
WPL	Work package leader

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BACKGROUND ABOUT WORM

WORM aims to design guidelines and support actions for circular economy in the humanitarian sector. It integrates bio-based technological solutions, leverages procurement for waste reduction, improves waste management methods and prioritises the sustainable livelihoods of waste pickers. WORM focuses on two selected settings: field hospital deployments and humanitarian livelihood programmes with a waste picking component. Following a collaborative and multi-actor approach, WORM brings together medical and humanitarian organisations, procurement service providers, logistics providers, waste management services and academic partners.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document is a deliverable of the WORM Project, funded under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101135392.

The aim of this document is to establish WORM's data management plan (DMP). The DMP builds on the principles of FAIRness, transparency and accessibility, taking EU and different national obligations into account. The DMP identifies all data collected, processed and/or generated by the project, analyses their main generators and users, and defines how data is handled during and after the project. It details the organisation, description, storage, sharing, and publication of the research data used in this research project, and specifies the key actions for ethical and legal compliance and FAIR data production. It describes the data management life cycle according to the HEU DMP template.

This deliverable (D10.1) as part of Task 10.3 is an updated version of WORM's DMP for the second interim period of the project. It builds on a previous DMP (D9.2) that has been submitted M6 of the project and that was followed up on in all WORM general assembly meetings, incorporating the comments of an external ethics review at the end of the first interim period and other new relevant material.

NON-TECHNICAL SUMMARY

This Data Management Plan (DMP) is a guidebook which describes how the WORM project handles research data. It describes the essential properties of the research data used in WORM, measures for maintaining high ethical standards and complying with relevant legislation, data ownership and access rights, planned lifespan of the data, and a plan for publishing the data in line with the FAIR data principles.

The DMP describes how data is organised, described, stored, and shared. It identifies all data collected, processed or generated during and after the project. The DMP has set out guidelines for the consortium on how to safely and securely handle personal data in accordance with the national and EU ethics and legal requirements including the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), and developed provisional guidelines on how to implement the FAIR principles to the datasets.

All research partners are responsible for complying with good data management practices and guidelines on the management and sharing of research data, data security and data protection in accordance with relevant legislation and research integrity. At the same time, researchers shall ensure the transparency and reusability of research materials produced and used in this project in line with the FAIR data principles.

The DMP as a living document will be updated and enriched as the project evolves. This version is an updated DMP for the second interim period of the project.

INTRODUCTION

This document is a deliverable of the WORM Project, funded under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101135392. This deliverable (D10.1), corresponding to task 10.3, presents WORM's updated data management plan (DMP) and is the first output from Work Package 10 (WP10). Led by the Hanken School of Economics (Hanken), WP10 focuses on the project management of WORM, including data management.

The DMP delineates the essential aspects of collecting, processing, storing, sharing, and publishing the data in WORM. It builds on the principles of FAIRness, transparency and accessibility, taking EU and different national obligations into account. The DMP identifies all the data collected, processed and/or generated by the project, analyses their main generators and users, and defines how data is handled during and after the project. It describes the data management life cycle according to the HEU DMP template, as well as ensuring that robust protocols for data security are established to safeguard personal information (in line with the GDPR), maintaining data quality as well as confidentiality. Equally important, the DMP identifies the key actions for FAIR data production, ensuring the findability and citability of the research data according to the FAIR data principles, while sees to that the degree of data openness and sharing is ethically and legally justifiable.

The aim of the DMP is thus to be a description of the datasets within the WORM project, but also to provide guidelines on data management to the WORM consortium. The guidelines defined in this DMP shall be followed by the WORM consortium to ensure that research data are collected, transferred, analysed, shared or otherwise processed in a secure setting, that use of the data is compliant with ethical and legal requirements, and that the openness, discoverability, and reusability of our research data are promoted as much as possible. The DMP starts with a general description of the data processed in the project (Section 2). Section 2 discusses the implementation of FAIR data principles. In Section 3, guidelines are provided for the consortium on the allocation of resources. Section 4 describes how to ensure data storage, backup, transfers, and archival in a secure way. Section 5 elaborates ethical issues involved in the project and identifies the key measures for ethical and legal compliance. Section 6 outlines the legal aspects of data management and includes a new section on local ethics registration in Kenya.

The first version of WORM's DMP (D9.2) had been submitted as the project's first deliverable. This updated version (D10.1) follows up from it and integrates comments from WORM's external ethics advisor (especially D11.3), and discussions throughout WORM's GA meetings (the last one at HNPW 2025 on March 24, 2025), and new ethics clearances esp. for WP6 & WP8. This version particularly elaborates on new developments since D9.2 and refers to D9.2 for details where no updates were necessary.

The data management of WORM's first interim period has followed its original DMP (D9.2). As planned, data management during this period was discussed at all general assembly meetings of the project, revisiting any questions and ensuring that the DMP was adhered to. Ethics clearance for WORM was obtained together through the consortium lead's organisation, Hanken School of Economics. Appendices to the DMP included the data protection impact assessment (DPIA), informed consent form, and privacy notice (see D9.2 for those). Where needed, these were translated to local languages when implementing the project.

Overall, WORM collects data from different sources to be able to fulfil the aims of the project. As outlined in WORM's original DMP (D9.2), WP1 includes a scoping exercise and collects data for various WPs, establishes a baseline and feeds into further WPs. Joint data collection for all WPs ensured that the project established a common view and that the data answers to all research questions while being parsimonious and mindful of the time and effort it requires of end users to collect materials and answer to all questions of the consortium. D9.2 elaborated on the purposes of data collection across WORM, the types and

formats of data, its origin, data sizes and utility. It also includes WORM's FAIR data management principles, allocation of resources, data security, ethical and legal aspects.

This updated DMP (D10.1) builds on D9.2 but does not repeat all the details that remain unchanged throughout the entire project. Rather, the focus here is on the second interim project period, which focuses on phase 3 of the project, "Policy and Implementation". Thereby the focus is on the remaining WPs. These are:

- WP5 "Recycling and WM at field hospitals",
- WP6 "Mitigation and livelihoods",
- WP8 "Communication, final phase", and
- WP10 "Project management final phase 1".

The above WPs are all due M24. In addition, the final comments from the external ethics advisor in WP11 are to be submitted with the final project report (M26).

After the first interim period, WORM also received comments from the external ethics advisor (D11.3). This updated DMP (D10.1) incorporates those comments, especially in section 6 regarding data security. Other comments are related to the safety of researchers while carrying out fieldwork and are part of WORM's risk assessment.

1. DATA SUMMARY

WP1's scoping exercise has established a common dataset and baseline for the WORM project, following the original DMP. In interim period 2 (M13-M24), complementary data is collected in WPs 5, 6, and 8, while data from the first interim period is still available to these WPs.

This section provides a general description of the further data collected and generated in the second interim period of the WORM project and of the purpose of the data collection/generation, data types and formats, secondary data reused, origin of the data, data size, and data utility.

1.1. Purpose of the data collection/generation

The primary purpose of the data collection/generation in WORM is to gather insights and information relevant to the project's objectives. WORM's overall objective is designing guidelines and support actions for circular economy in the humanitarian sector. WORM focuses on two selected settings: field hospital deployments, and humanitarian livelihood programmes with a waste picking component. Across these settings, the project focuses on several cross-cutting focus areas:

- the integration of bio-based technological innovation solutions in the humanitarian context,
- using procurement as a gatekeeper for waste avoidance, and gateway to integrate innovative solutions,
- improvements in waste management, and the use of less polluting waste treatment methods,
- a specific focus on the sustainable livelihoods of waste pickers, and
- policy development, advocacy, and a heightened local awareness of improved WM in the relevant local contexts.

WORM's second interim period focuses on the development of standard operational procedures (SOPs) and medical waste management guidelines for field hospitals (WP5), the development of a causal loop diagram (CLD) that also highlights the potential limitations of bio-based solutions, and the development of a policy framework for sustainable humanitarian livelihood programmes especially with regards to the livelihoods of waste pickers (WP6). WP8 supports the second interim period with targeted local awareness campaigns.

1.2. Data types and formats

To design guidelines and support actions for circular economy in the humanitarian sector, the WORM project engages in data collection from primary and secondary sources. This involves obtaining qualitative data through surveys and interviews with experts in the field, in addition to quantitative data from suppliers and waste management practitioners to carry out the LCAs. Expertise is needed across various areas: production, procurement, innovation, waste management and waste treatment, and across two distinct settings: field hospitals and clinics; and livelihoods programmes.

WORM data comes in the types and formats of:

- quantitative and qualitative survey data in .xlsx, .csv and .txt formats,
- interview data (semi-structured interviews, focus groups), audio recordings in .mp3 and .wav, transcripts in .docx, .txt, .pdf
- quantitative data from ERP systems and waste management systems, in .xlsx, .csv, .pdf
- secondary waste stream data from field hospitals / clinic deployments, in .docx, .txt, .xlsx, .csv, .pdf
- process descriptions (e.g. procurement processes, waste treatment processes), in docx, .pdf, .jpg, .png, .xml, .ppt, and
- policy documents in .pdf and .ppt formats.
- empirical observations (qualitative and/or quantitative) taken from site-visits, noted as field notes in .docx, .txt, .xlsx, .csv, .pdf

WORM's second interim period complements the data from the first interim period with procedural data for the SOPs of field hospital deployment and handover. In other words, WORM data includes procedural data, quantitative data on product groups and their respective waste streams; quantitative data on inputs for production and waste management; surveys; audio data from interviews, as well as text data from documents and interview transcripts. This is complemented by figures drawn in workshops and seminars.

Preference has been given to open, standard, and non-proprietary data formats to facilitate common usage and long-term reuse of the data. File types and formats are determined in a way that enables data sharing and interoperability with existing systems and co-ordination platforms, etc. At the end of the project, the pseudonymised data¹ will be deposited into the open platform Zenodo in non-proprietary formats (e.g., plain text).

1.3. Existing data reused

Besides data collected from surveys and interviews, WORM combines and reuses publicly available data (e.g. policy documents, data from scientific literature for the LCAs and CLDs), and data from the systems of WORM end users:

- quantitative data from ERP systems and waste management systems,
- secondary data from scientific literature,
- secondary waste stream data from field hospitals / clinic deployments,
- process descriptions (e.g. procurement processes, waste treatment processes), and
- policy documents.

WORM's second interim period reuses the data from the first interim period, especially the baseline data from WP1.

1.4. Origin of the data

WORM uses publicly available open data as well as collects primary data from various respondents and stakeholders. Also in the second interim period, primary data is collected using social scientific methods, in particular semi-structured interviews and focus group interviews. Respondents are human subjects, from whom data is collected by means of direct interaction and/or observation either on-site at the stakeholders' place of work or via Teams. Furthermore, procedural data is collected from end user organisations as process descriptions, current SOPs and waste management guidelines.

In the context of WORM, a research participant engages directly with the project by answering questions in an interview. The data is collected via interviews and surveys, and other stakeholder engagement activities (e.g. interactive webinars or in-person focus groups/interviews) for transcription and further analysis. In some cases, the data will be transcribed with automate methods which are encrypted both in transit and at rest and only the account owner has access to and control over the data.

Data collection procedures used include:

- documents and process descriptions collected from WORM end users
- policy documents from WORM end users and donors
- waste types and quantities from waste audits or field hospitals / health care centres studied
- expert interviews
- surveys with suppliers and waste management experts
- focus groups with people in waste management
- stakeholder workshops
- site visits at stakeholder's place of work

Expert interviews, focus groups, and stakeholder workshops are accompanied by the WORM privacy notice and informed consent forms from the original DMP. Analysis methods include thematic analysis, procedural analysis, life cycle assessment, waste stream analysis, and causal loop diagrams.

1.5. Data size

Data size varies depending on the data types:

- survey data, usually <1MB files each,
- interview data, <1-2MB files each,
- quantitative data, <1-20MB files each,
- secondary waste stream data from field hospitals / clinic deployments, <1-20MB files each,
- process descriptions, 10-20MB files each,
- policy documents, 5-20MB files each,
- pictures, figures, <5MB files each.

1.6. Data utility

The research data can be useful to the principal stakeholder categories targeted by WORM's dissemination and communication activities:

- professionals in field hospital deployments and humanitarian livelihood programmes with a waste picking component,
- waste pickers,
- government (local, national, EU, other) including public authorities,

- (medical) humanitarian sector,
- Industry (suppliers and service providers to the humanitarian sector),
- research community,
- media, and
- the general public.

2. FAIR DATA MANAGEMENT

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

To make the data easily findable, the project will archive the digital data in Zenodo and use descriptive metadata as required and provided by the data storage repository.

The research project will also make sure that properly documented metadata of research data is published by using the Fairdata Qvain metadata tool. Qvain is part of the Fairdata services to support research data to go FAIR. The services are offered by the Finnish Ministry of Education and Culture and produced by CSC – IT centre for research in Finland. The open research data and associated metadata will be assigned unique DOI (digital object identifiers) in Zenodo and Qvain, which enables (meta)data uniquely identifiable, and thus accessible and referenceable. Data will further be documented in a readme file to ensure that it is fully and correctly interpreted.

Metadata will include content about data title, creators, contact information, dates, data subjects/keywords, funders, licenses, languages, geographic locations, abbreviations or codes used in the dataset, methodology used in data collection/generation, instrument and protocol information, survey tool details, and version information. Properly describing and documenting data enables users, as well as the research members, to understand and track important details of the research, and facilitates data search and retrieval in the data repository.

Files and folders will be versioned and structured by using a name convention consisting of project name, dataset name, and version information. The WORM project management handbook (D9.1) has defined the naming conventions for documents including the coding of release numbers as follows:

For deliverables, the file name must start with WORM and contain the following elements as a minimum:

- WORM-Dnumber_Short-Title_VersionNumber
- Example: WORM-D9.1 project management handbook v1.0.pdf

The WORM SharePoint is set up to automatically save revisions, and it is paramount that people adding to the document also note their names and what they have altered in the revision table in the beginning of the document. New release numbers are used for major changes only.

For all other project documents, the file name must start with WORM and contain the following elements as a minimum:

WORM-Title_ReleaseNumber

Example: WORM-kick off agenda 25.1.2024

Where:

- WORM: the project acronym
- Kick-off agenda: title of document
- 25.1.2024: release number / date

Search keywords and subject headings from the KOKO Ontology (integrated in the Qvain metadata tool) will be provided to optimise data reuse possibilities.

2.2. Making data openly accessible

As already specified in the WORM grant agreement, open science (OS) principles are key both for the project and the community behind it. OS is the key idea guiding scientific dissemination in WORM. The WORM consortium encourages early sharing of research outputs (data and publications) in an open, transparent, and re-usable fashion, contributes to increasing the quality of research results and maximises the impact for society. OS is a key part of the research design of the WORM proposal. During the last years, the OS policy of the European Commission has been designed around eight ambitions, set by the Open Science Policy Platform¹⁹ in 2020: (1) Rewards and Incentives; (2) Indicators & Next-Generation Metrics; (3) Future of Scholarly Communications; (4) European Open Science Cloud (EOSC); (5) FAIR Data; (6) Research Integrity; (7) Skills & Education; (8) Citizen Science. Each of these ambitions affects the modus operandi of research funding agencies, research performing institutions, entities responsible for scholarly communication, and research evaluation agencies. The eight ambitions are taken into consideration for the work throughout WORM's project cycle: data collection, analysis, recommendations, and validation. WORM implements open, transparent, and reusable methodologies, and documents them to ensure replicability. All research data collected and/or processed during the project length follow a creating-processing-analysing-preserving-giving-access life cycle.

WORM's commitment to open science practices leads to the plan for specific data management actions. The issue of FAIR principles guide data collection procedures in all WPs. WPL will be involved from the very beginning of the project in order to define how to implement the 'FAIR' approach defined by the EC ("findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable"). The consortium will work towards releasing the data used, collected, processed, and generated in the open platform Zenodo. The WORM project can be found on Zenodo at https://zenodo.org/communities/worm_eu/ and on the repositories of WORM partner universities. All public deliverables of the project are also on Zenodo. Webinar and stakeholder meeting recordings are at WORM's Youtube channel at https://www.youtube.com/@WORM_EUproject

With the research participant's permission, after all direct identifiers are removed and indirect identifiers removed or categorised, data collected during the course of the project will be made openly available on the project website, in presentations at conferences, in the project deliverables, and in journal and practitioner articles. Data in the pseudonymised form will be submitted to and archived in Zenodo in accordance with their services, for the purpose of allowing other researchers as well as scientific publication outlets to conduct further scientific analyses on the data. Any part of data with personal identifiers and/or geolocations or for which a respondent has not consented to its archival will not be submitted for archival.

All tools, software, and components in WORM needed to use the raw data to validate research results will be available as open source under appropriate licences. There will be no restrictions on use and access to the open data. Separately, access to, and the use of software, tools and platforms that constitute background are noted the consortium agreement, which stipulates their licencing agreements and duration of licences to the duration of the project. See section 7 for the legal aspects of the project.

2.3. Making data interoperable

All data processed in the project will use non-proprietary formats with standard representations (Unicode) and meet the requirements: non-proprietary; open, documented standard; common usage by research community; standard representation (ASCII, Unicode); and uncompressed.

When depositing data in Zenodo, the project will ensure that the research data is migrated to new formats, platforms, and storage media as required by good open science practices to enable data sharing, reuse, and interoperability between researchers, institutions, organisations, and countries, while commonly used, non-proprietary, and parsable file formats have been selected to support the interoperability of the data.

Crucially, all WORM outputs are designed to be cost-effective and open source as far as privacy allows, thereby supporting those organisations where resources may be limited and ensuring data reuse and interoperability. Standard, controlled vocabularies will be used for describing all variables, and for labelling, indexing or categorising datasets. Furthermore, the WORM project will use common social science data collection methods and practices, which also contributes to data interoperability.

2.4. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)

The consortium will save the pseudonymised data in a non-proprietary format (e.g., plain text) and deposit them into Zenodo or university repositories after the data has been cleaned and pseudonymised. Good practice developed by the Zenodo team can ensure the ongoing integrity and validity of the data deposited.

A creative commons license CC-BY (requiring attribution) or CC-0 (no rights reserved) will be used for all of WORM's document-based outputs (e.g., deliverables) and open research data, free of charge for any user and without any embargo period, to ensure that they are shared with minimal restrictions, aside from attribution to the authors or creators. The project's outputs will be made available on the WORM website and/or through open access publications. The documents will be available under a CC BY licence and the data will be available as public domain (CC0) to facilitate reuse. Data will be described with rich metadata, and registered or indexed in searchable resources wherever possible. The resources will also be linked with OABT entries to encourage findability and reuse.

Regarding its DCE activities, WORM engages and involves the WORM consortium and identified stakeholders in the co-design and co-creation of the project outputs, thus promoting OS practices and responsible research and innovation values through its open validation process. Amongst the dissemination activities, WORM consortium members will produce academic/research papers that will be published in Open Research Europe (ORE) or in open access scientific journals and shared in Zenodo, under a CC BY licence. Authors will retain the intellectual property rights to comply with the open access obligations of Horizon Europe, persistent identifiers in the publications will be used (like ORCID for authors, and the Funder Registry for the EC as the funding agency), and the name of the action, the acronym, and the grant number amongst the metadata will be referenced. Authors will guarantee that metadata will be provided as a public domain dedication (CC0) both in the journal and in the open access repositories where they are archived. Underlying research data will be linked to the publications through their DOIs, and will be published under the principle of 'as open as possible and as closed as necessary', and pseudonymise any identifiers, and published either in the same journal, when possible, or in Zenodo as CC0 thus making them follow the FAIR20 principles. Target journals will be selected based on OS principles. For example, the Journal of Humanitarian Logistics and Supply Chain Management, has a new OS policy without any fees to authors. In all cases, gold open access is targeted; and/or post prints of publications are available through university repositories.

To ensure the quality and consistency of the data, transcriptions of audio interviews will be checked by someone other than the transcriber/transcription service provider, analogue materials be digitised in as high resolution as possible for accuracy, and dates of data collection, retrieval, and changes be recorded, making all data related actions traceable and repeatable. Data protection measures such as minimisation, pseudonymisation, and pseudonymisation will not affect data quality. In all conversions, maintaining the original information content will be ensured.

3. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

This is the updated DMP for the second interim period of the WORM project. The PI being at Hanken, Hanken's research support unit provides assistance with data management and management of IPRs.

The project PI is responsible for the initial planning and execution of data management procedures, and all WPLs for the implementation of these procedures. All researchers working for the project are responsible for the tasks of data collection, data storage and backup, data documentation and sharing, and all consortium members and their team members are expected to comply with this data management strategy including related legislation. The onboarding of new team members includes the DMP, requiring them to adopt all its rules before starting their work in the team, and find all relevant material on the WORM SharePoint. In WORM, data management is reviewed internally, at the respective institutional levels of research organisations, at general assembly meetings, and by an independent ethics consultant. A first external ethics review took place in M14 (D11.3), the next one is at the end of the project (M26).

In the following sections, guidelines are described for research partners to follow in case of datasets with personal data. All research partners ought to follow these guidelines and procedures, and bear the responsibilities for legal, ethical, and moral concerns and decisions involved in the research and during the interaction between the researcher and research participants. For each dataset, a responsible person has been appointed at the partner level, who will be held accountable for this specific dataset. All researchers shall describe their datasets containing personal data and share the description with the data protection officer (DPO) at their own organisation, in line with the GDPR (Art. 24, 28).

The research project has also allocated time and budget to complete the data management tasks and cover relevant costs. Archival in the repository Zenodo and metadata production through Qvain are both free of charge. The data management tasks altogether will accompany the entire project throughout.

WORM does not consider the long-term preservation of the research data. Research data will be preserved internally at least until the publications from WORM are under process, and externally on Zenodo and/or university repositories.

4. DATA SECURITY

WORM agrees on and disseminates the joint data security guidelines to all research partners to ensure that data is securely stored and managed. Besides each institution's data security instructions, the research team members shall follow these joint rules of the consortium. Appropriate technical and organisational measures are implemented to ensure data security and prevent risks faced by the data subjects in the event of unauthorised access to, or disclosure, accidental deletion or destruction of, their data. In case of a security incident, the DPOs will work closely together with data security officers of the participating universities.

For secure data storage and backup, the WORM consortium stores the information received from interviews, workshops, surveys, etc., in password-protected personal computers (company computers for personal use) and a joint secured SharePoint (based within Hanken's Teams) with appropriate security restrictions in place. As also requested by the external ethics advisor (D11.3), Hanken's IT team supports with matters of cybersecurity and advises of the handling of sensitive information. This includes access restrictions to IT systems and storage such as password protection, encryption, etc., by complying with all national and EU legislations. Hanken-provided systems do automatic backups. Data is retrievable in case of human error or data corruption. In addition, manual backups of master data files are taken regularly and always before any major file-format or data conversions.

For secure data transfers, sharing of transcripts across the consortium members that need access to the data for various types of analysis is only via the joint SharePoint. Closed channels on Teams are created for data that is still being processed for pseudonymisation.

Special attention has been paid to the GDPR when handling data from non-EU countries. Field research is carried out in Kenya and Vietnam. Researchers are deployed with humanitarian organisations that are experienced in these environments. Their security protocols and duty of care apply. Furthermore, many of the researchers are members of rosters of humanitarian organisations and have themselves experience from previous deployments, and the necessary security trainings for these. Further security protocols are developed for field research in the second interim period. As pointed out by the external ethics advisor (D11.3), WORM will develop a risk assessment, safety and security protocol for field research. This includes aspects of travel advisory, the security and safety of researchers, as well as considerations of data and equipment security.

After data has been collected in Kenya and Vietnam, it is translated and transcribed by local transcription/translation service providers in the same country, and then uploaded to the WORM SharePoint under the WP for which it was collected. The files in the recorders are then irretrievably deleted. Rights to access the data and data usage are then controlled by the PI with the support of the project management office. The PI completes the list of users and all rights granted, and a procedure for withdrawing rights. Access to data is only granted to authenticated research members of the project. Access to the identifiable data will be restricted to those researchers directly involved in the project.

WORM partners outside the EU involved in data analysis (RMIT Vietnam, PSA) have access to the pseudonymised data in the shared secure WORM SharePoint. No personal data is transferred outside the EU/EEA or to international organisations, and personal data processing and transfers only reside inside the EU/EEA and are limited to the research. Access control is in line with the level of confidentiality involved. Personal data is protected with adequate, appropriate safeguard measures such as encryption and strict access control, and will not be sent between research team members by email or other types of file transfers.

The project enters into agreements including a data processing agreement (DPA) and/or a non-disclosure agreement with all service providers who conduct translation/interpretation or transliteration/transcription work which contains any personal or individual-specific data or is based on any individual informants. The WORM SharePoint is covered by Hanken's DPA with its service providers. The consortium's data processing agreements are covered by the WORM consortium agreement that all beneficiaries have signed.

The pseudonymised data will be archived into the certified, trustworthy data repository Zenodo and/or university repositories.

5. ETHICAL ASPECTS

5.1. Data protection

The participation of different types of stakeholders in WORM's activities means that personal data, or data that can identify participating stakeholders, are collected by members of the consortium. Data is collected from expert interviews, focus groups with people in waste management, and stakeholder workshops, combined with secondary data from ERP systems and waste management systems, field hospitals / clinic deployments, process descriptions, and policy documents. Personal data can be found in the survey data and audio data from interviews with professionals in humanitarian organisations and waste treatment organisations, hospital waste management staff, people involved in waste management, and procurement experts.

The project co-ordinator acts as the data controller who ensures that WORM's activities are compliant with EU rules and regulations. The co-ordinator Hanken has appointed a Data Protection Officer (DPO) from whom project WORM obtains advice about data protection obligations and how to meet them. The DPO's contact details are given to all the data subjects involved in the collection and processing of the above-mentioned personal data types, as well as of the secondary data type if applicable. All research partners and service providers follow relevant ethical and legal requirements and implement WORM's technical and organisational data protection measures.

WORM specifies that the following direct identifiers – name, e-mail address, facial image (e.g. picture, video footage showing the face), voice recording – can be collected from the respondents and stored encrypted on the WORM SharePoint until transcribed and pseudonymised, where they are safely managed according to the DMP. Separate questions are asked from respondents in the informed consent sheet about each of these aspects, as well as in the recording of webinars.

WORM will have a mailing list that respondents and other stakeholders can sign up for. This is upon their own discretion. The mailing list is for the purposes of dissemination in the project and is not used for cross-identifications with respondents. Only the dissemination partner (Euronovia) maintains the WORM mailing list. The collected contact information of research participants which is not linked to files containing other personal data, is stored securely in a separate shared file with restricted access.

Even though WORM focuses on a field hospital setting, data is collected from experts through interviews and surveys, from ERP systems, from waste streams, and in forms of documents, but not from patients. WORM does not collect any medical data of any respondents. No special categories of personal data (sensitive personal data, GDPR Art. 9-10) such as personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, trade union membership, criminal offences, genetic data, biometric data processed solely to identify a human being, health-related data, data concerning a person's sex life or sexual orientation, and personal data relating to criminal convictions and offences or related security measures, and no data of a highly person will be involved in the project.

If a data subject by own initiative discloses sensitive data to the representative of the project, such information should be by default not be stored or transferred further. In case a member of the WORM team would intentionally or unintentionally be given access to any form of sensitive data, is the person obligated to a strict non-disclosure and to absolutely refrain from any ways to use, transfer, store or exploit the sensitive data.

Data of interest to WORM relate to materials and their adequate waste management, to procurement and to innovation. Data that is not relevant for the project will not be asked about. If any such data comes up in an interview, it will be removed in the pseudonymisation process.

To respect and protect the fundamental rights of the data subjects, the WORM project adopts adequate technical and organisational measures for data protection by design and default and monitors continuously if these measures are implemented appropriately to ensure that ethical standards and guidelines within Horizon Europe and all relevant national and European legislations are rigorously applied, regardless of where the research is conducted. The consortium has performed a data protection impact assessment (DPIA, see D9.2) and will keep records of all data processing activities. Policies and procedures have been established about how to limit the use of data and minimise data collection, how to inform the data subjects, how to pseudonymise or anonymise data wherever possible, how to deal with complaints and data breaches, and how to perform data erasure within the specified time periods. WORM identifies the legal basis for personal data processing and ensure that adequate level of protection and appropriate safeguards are applied during data storage, transferal, sharing, and preservation. The project enters into agreements including a data processing agreement (DPA) with all service providers. The WORM SharePoint is covered by Hanken's DPA with its service providers. The consortium's data

processing agreements are covered by the WORM consortium agreement that all beneficiaries have signed.

Data protection by design is implemented in practice during the active research phase in the following aspects:

- **Clarify the legal basis for processing.** The purpose of the dataset and legal basis for data processing in this project is scientific research carried out in the public interest. In addition, in accordance with ethical standards, project WORM asks for informed consent of the research participants when collecting and processing personal data, as well as secondary data if applicable. Respondents can withdraw their consent at any time. Consent for using material for communication purposes is obtained separately (separate point respondents can opt in for). If it is unrealistic to get informed consent sheets (plan B only), research members ask twice for consent in an interview: once before asking whether recording can be made, and then repeat the question on recording. All signed consent sheets are kept on file and stored with the data under each WP and can be provided upon request.
- **Inform the data subjects with sufficient information on the processing of their personal data.** The project will use Hanken's e-form privacy notice. Each respondent will receive such a privacy notice prior to data collection. The privacy notice describes what personal data will be collected from each respondent as a participating individual, and why and how the personal data will be processed in the research, as well as the details of the research project and related participation. It also provides information on what rights each respondent as the data subject has pertaining to the personal data and how s/he can exercise these rights in relation to the processing. For ensuring the enforcement of data subjects' rights, all research partners will provide privacy notice to each participant and ask for informed consent from each of them. Joint and shared measures and arrangements are made to enable data subjects to fulfil and exercise their fundamental rights. (See D9.2 for the informed consent and privacy notices of the project.)
- **Keep records of data processing activities.** Records of data processing activities by both the data controller and data processors are drawn up and kept on file, and can be, if needed, accessible to data subjects, research funder/Commission services, or data protection supervisory authorities.
- **Sign a data processing agreement (DPA).** All data processors who conduct translation/interpretation or transliteration/transcription work, which contains any personal or individual-specific data, or are based on any individual informants shall sign a data processing agreement (DPA). The WORM consortium agreement covers the data processing of research partners.
- **Implement data minimisation.** WORM's data protection policy implements the principles of purpose limitation and data minimisation in a comprehensive way, covering research, education, infrastructure, and partnerships. Project WORM only collects and processes data that are necessary and proportionate to achieve the tasks of this project. Personal data will only be processed for the scientific research purpose and will not be used for any other purposes that are not considered to be compatible with this original scientific research purpose.
A data minimisation review has been conducted by the research partners at the meeting at HNPW 2024 for the whole process of data management, including defining the amount of personal data collected, the extent to which they may be accessed, further processed and shared, the purposes for which they are used, and the period for which they are kept.

- **Pseudonymise the data wherever possible.** Pseudonymisation is performed as soon as possible, for instance, right after the data has been aggregated and before data analysis to protect the data subjects' privacy and minimise the risk to their fundamental rights. The additional information on the original values and techniques used to create the pseudonyms or codes is kept organisationally and technically separately from the pseudonymised data to ensure that the personal data are not attributed to an identified or identifiable natural person.
Interview transcripts, documents, and procedural data obtained from various stakeholders in the consortium are pseudonymised for data analysis. Names for first identification have been pseudonymised to position, expertise, type of organisation, and country. As agreed in the meeting at HNPW2024, **the pseudonymisation key includes country, type of organisation, expertise, date, e.g., KEHUMWM20240607. Three types of country denominations will be used: KE (Kenya), VN (Vietnam), and ROW (rest of the world).** A key of the informants is kept separately from pseudonymised transcripts but use the same pseudonyms in both.
Any data with personal identifiers will be pseudonymised before sharing and data analysis. Any organisation-specific numerical and procedural data that is collected will also be pseudonymised in all deliverables and publications.
- **Ensure data security.** Appropriate technical and organisational measures are implemented to ensure data security and prevent risks faced by the data subjects in the event of unauthorised access to, or disclosure, accidental deletion or destruction of, their data. See section 5.
- **Data from and to non-EU countries.** The research team members rigorously maintain high ethical standards and comply with relevant legislations, regardless of the country in which the research is carried out and data are collected and processed. Project WORM ensures that when collecting personal data outside the EU and when transferring personal data from a non-EU country to the EU (or another third state), data processing activities fully comply with the EU legislations and national laws of any country in which the research is conducted and the data collected. After personal data has been collected in a non-EU country, it is translated and transcribed by local transcription/translation service providers in the same country, and then uploaded to the WORM Teams under the WP for which it was collected. The files in the recorders are then irretrievably deleted. No personal data will then be transferred outside the EU/EEA or to international organisations, and personal data processing and transfers only reside inside the EU/EEA and are limited to the research.
- **Data erasure and data sharing.** The WORM project makes sure that personal data, dispensable data files, temporary files created when programs are used, and all their back-ups shall be deleted within due time when they are no longer needed, and that the deleted data cannot be recovered. All the personal data will be erased within five years after the completion of the research project. With the research participant's permission, the consortium will share and archive the pseudonymised data in Zenodo for any users to access, mine, exploit, reproduce, and disseminate free of charge.

5.2. Ethical dimension of the objectives, methodology and likely impact

WORM focuses on waste management in the humanitarian context. By introducing alternative bio-based products and materials, it seeks to reduce environmental damage, but it may impact negatively on livelihoods. WORM elucidates such potential negative implications in a causal loop diagram. Different alternative waste treatment methods and their environmental impact are studied in the project. The humanitarian context targets most vulnerable populations. Even though workshops will be held for vulnerable populations (e.g. waste pickers), no data will be collected from these, but instead, from

humanitarian organisations. WORM adheres to all humanitarian principles which include humanity (and thereby non-discrimination), and impartiality.

Vulnerable populations (esp. waste pickers) will be targeted through local awareness campaigns (WP8 in the second interim period of the project). Campaigns will engage waste handlers, community groups, county representatives, health workers, and teachers, who in turn can include campaign materials at schools. WORM will head the advice of its humanitarian end users before engaging with any vulnerable populations. In all data collection, and in the local awareness campaigns, active informed consent will be sought. Participation in the project is at all times fully voluntary, and participants have the right to withdraw and terminate their participation.

WORM's use case setting of field hospitals includes a focus on medical, and thereby potentially toxic and hazardous waste. The project focuses inherently on the development of less toxic waste treatment practices and engages scientists familiar with safety and hygiene precautions in their evaluation. WORM advocates for the proper use of personal protective equipment also for its own researchers.

WORM includes project members from low- and middle-income countries. They play an important role in the implementation of the project and in the organisation of local awareness campaigns. They, and several other members of the WORM consortium, are engaged with Horizon Europe project for the first time. Therefore, WORM is implementing the system of work package leads with co-leads, actively building the capacity of its consortium to implement such projects.

5.3. Compliance with ethical principles and relevant legislations

All of WORM's activities are compliant with EU rules and regulations. Waste management legislation and treatment possibilities differ across WORM implementation countries. This is in fact one of the focus areas of WORM, seeking to improve waste management practices, evaluating alternatives, and running local awareness campaigns for their improvement.

WORM adheres to the Vancouver protocol with regards to publications, co-authoring, and rights to data and publications, and follows the guidelines and best practices of the Finnish National Board on Research Integrity (TENK). WORM's research protocol has been approved by Hanken's research ethics board on Feb 21, 2024. The development of data collection instruments and the data management plan are guided by Hanken's research ethics board and Data protection officer.

Further ethics issues were identified as a result of the ethics evaluations. These are dealt with under WP11. An external independent ethics advisor has been appointed for this purpose and will submit a report at the end of each reporting period. The project, and the report, shall pay attention to:

- A data management plan for personal data, the processing and sharing of such data and the time period of its retention.
- The potential biohazard risks connected with dangerous waste coming also from hospitals and vulnerable populations.
- The potential geopolitical risks for research staff when working in potentially unstable countries.
- The safety rules for research staff, as shall be elaborated on and agreed on at the beginning of WP7.

The Consortium confirms that compliance with ethical principles and applicable international, EU and national law in the implementation of research activities not originally envisaged (or not described in detail) in the DoA will be ensured. The Consortium also confirms that any ethical concerns raised by those activities will be handled by following rigorously the recommendations provided in the European Commission Ethics Self-Assessment Guidelines.

5.4. Local ethics registration in Kenya

While the WORM project overall did not require an ethical review as per TENK standards 2019, ethics clearance was nonetheless sought and obtained through the consortium lead's organisation, Hanken School of Economics.

However, research in Kenya that will be carried out in the second interim period of the project necessitates local ethics registration, hence Pamela Steele Associates (PSA) as WORM's local partner facilitated this through the Institutional Scientific Ethics Review Committee of the Jaramogi Oginga Odinga Teaching and Referral Hospital. The reasons for this selection are

- WORM's focus on waste management in field hospitals,
- The ethics clearance of a health care organisation includes an understanding of any health and safety hazards, and
- Medical ethics clearance being the most stringent.

That said, WORM does not expose researchers to medical waste; instead, it advocates for the use of personal protective equipment, which is one of the five priority product groups of the project. WORM does also not collect nor analyse any sensitive data such as health data.

The process of Ethical Clearance for research in Kenya;

1. Submission of protocol to the Institutional Ethics Review Committee

The full protocol and supporting documents (The research proposal, concept note for data collection, signed consent forms to be used during the research, WORM ethical clearance, filled research form by the PI and Co-researchers, Curriculum Vitae of the researchers and proof of payment) were submitted to the Ethics Review Committee of the Jaramogi Oginga Odinga Teaching and Referral Hospital (JOOTRH). This Committee is accredited by the National Commission for Science, Technology and Innovation (NACOSTI) to evaluate the ethical compliance in research involving Human participants.

2. Acknowledgment of receipt

Upon submission, the ERC issued an acknowledgement email confirming receipt of the application. This serves as proof that the review process is underway, which takes up to 21 working days.

3. Review and clearance process

The JOOTRH-ERC reviews the research protocol for ethical compliance, potential risk to participants, data protection strategies and adherence to Kenyan cultural and legal standards. If any comments are given by reviewers, they must be addressed before approval is done.

4. Issuance of ethical clearance certificate

A formal ethical clearance certificate is issued, once the application meets all the required criteria. The certificate is compulsory for any researcher intending to conduct field work.

5. Research permit from National Commission for Science, Technology and Innovation (NACOSTI)

For foreign researchers, an additional research permit must be obtained from NACOSTI. This application can only proceed after the ethical clearance is granted by the Institutional Review Committee (JOOTRH-ERC). The process is done online and involves submitting a copy of the ethical clearance certificate, researchers' identification documents (valid passport), institutional supporting letter (Hanken School of Economics), researchers curriculum vitae and paying the research permit fee. This research permit authorizes foreign nationals to conduct research in Kenya. It typically takes 7-14 working days to be processed once submission is done.

6. Field research protocol compliance

All approved research must adhere to the ethical conditions outlined in the certificate, including consent processes, anonymization of data and confidentiality of the participants. Local partners (PSA) assist with ensuring compliance with the approved methods.

See the annexes to the updated DMP for the documents of this local ethics registration.

6. LEGAL ASPECTS

The WORM grant agreement and consortium agreement cover all legal aspects of the project. This includes agreements on authorship, ownership, access rights, exploitation, dissemination, and IPR. The consortium agreement further specifies the structure of the project, and accordingly, sets that the WORM General Assembly as the highest decision-making body of the project that makes consortium-level decisions including any potential requests for changes to these agreements. As stipulated by the WORM project management handbook (D9.1), all contractual documents are found on the WORM SharePoint. The terms and provisions of the grant agreement and its annexes, and the WORM consortium agreement will prevail in the event of any inconsistencies with the information and rules also in the DMP.

The WORM consortium agreement further stipulates that prior notice of any planned publication shall be given to the other Parties at least 45 calendar days before the publication. Any objection to the planned publication shall be made in accordance with the Grant Agreement by written notice to the Co-ordinator and to the Party or Parties proposing the dissemination within 30 calendar days after receipt of the notice. If no objection is made within the time limit stated above, the publication is permitted. For the case of any disagreements, conflict resolution mechanisms are detailed in the WORM project management handbook (D9.1).

IPR rules conform to HEU regulations and principles. Authors will retain the IPRs to comply with the open access obligations of Horizon Europe. When reusing secondary data gathered from open sources, good practices for the attribution of authorship and data citation will be followed, and all legal restrictions such as copyright permissions and license terms on its use observed.

WORM ensures the exploitability of its results while contributing to open standards development. Access rights to results or background that are needed for exploitation are also agreed on in the WORM consortium agreement.

ANNEX 1 Ethics registration documents from Kenya

Telephone: 0724804676
E-mail: ercjootrh@go.ke

Website: www.jootrh.go.ke

**JARAMOGI OGINGA ODINGA TEACHING AND
REFERRAL HOSPITAL,
P.O. BOX 849,
KISUMU**

RESEARCH AND TRAINING FORM

JARAMOGI OGINGA ODINGA TEACHING AND REFERRAL HOSPITAL INSTITUTIONAL SCIENTIFIC ETHICS REVIEW COMMITTEE REQUIREMENTS FOR APPLICANTS

1. Submit your softcopy to our email: ercjootrh@gmail.com / iserc@jootrh.go.ke
2. The soft copies MUST be signed (original signatures) by PI/student and supervisors with current dates.
3. Payments to be done upon clearance from the ISERC Secretary as per the charges schedule.
4. Pay the prescribed review fees to the JOOTRH Accounts office/fee section and submit receipts to the research office.
5. Fill in the attached form to commit submission and sharing of your final research report with ISERC and JOOTRH.
6. You need to recognize JOOTRH-ISERC study approving institution under ethical approval section of your write up.
7. Upon approval of your study, seek clearance from NACOSTI and JOOTRH CEO before you start data collection.
8. Data collection process is the sole responsibility of the Principal Investigator
9. There is need to attach CV for PI, CO-PI's, budget, GDP, GCP approval from the school of post-graduate studies and timelines for your study (GHANT CHART).
10. All protocols should be submitted as scheduled to research office two weeks before the date of the meeting, see attached review periods (every last Thursday of the month).
11. The Principal Investigator should respond to comments raised by reviewers in within a maximum period of two weeks, failure to do this, first, second and third reminders will be sent to the PI and if still no response the new protocol will be required for re-submission.
12. All submitted protocols must be duly signed by both the PI and Supervisors.
13. Compress all softcopy documents as one pdf document.
14. Attach anti-plagiarism report in your protocol.
15. Upon approval, provide us with one bound hardcopy of the approved version of the protocol and send a replica PDF softcopy to our JOOTRH- ISERC email iserc@jootrh.go.ke.
16. Upon completion of your study, share a softcopy to ercjootrh@gmail.com. Make plans to conduct a Continuous Medical Education (CME) to disseminate your findings.
17. Renewal process to commence 60 days before expiry of the approval letter. Late renewals will attract a penalty

THANK YOU FOR COLLABORATING WITH US.

RESEARCH AND TRAINING FORM

NAME: Virva Tuomala
ADDRESS: Arkadiankatu 22 **E-MAIL ADDRESS:** virva.tuomala@hanken.fi
INSTITUTION OF STUDY Hanken School of Economics
ID/PASSPORT NO: CP2601468 **MOBILE:** +358503298987
CO-INVESTIGATOR/SUPERVISOR: Margot Rocheteau, Sarah Joseph

TITLE OF STUDY: Waste in humanitarian operations: Reduction and minimisation
(WORM)

DURATION OF STUDY: **From:** 01.01.2024 **To:** 31.12.2025

WHO WILL DO THE DATA COLLECTION? Virva Tuomala, Margot Rocheteau
and Sarah Joseph

(IF SOMEONE ELSE, GIVE NAME/NAMES): _____

PURPOSE OF THIS STUDY (Please be specific.)

Conduct interviews with relevant stakeholders (humanitarian organisations, hospital and healthcare experts) to collect data for the WORM project (Horizon Europe grant number 101135392).

You agree to abide by the conditions given to you for this study and you will maintain the order of the hospital during your study. Hospital reserves the right of stopping you from conducting the study if they find out that you are misusing the data for a wrong purpose other than the proposal of the study.

Name: Virva Tuomala

Signature: **Date:** 10.04.2025

**COUNTY GOVERNMENT OF KISUMU
DEPARTMENT OF HEALTH**

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Website: www.jootrh.go.ke

JARAMOGI OGINGA ODINGA TEACHING &
REFERRAL HOSPITAL
P.O. BOX 849
KISUMU

CHECK LIST FOR SUBMISSION OF PROTOCOLS/PROPOSALS TO THE JOTRH- ISERC

S/NO.	REQUIREMENTS	YES	NO
1.	SOFT COPY OF THE Protocol SUBMITTED online (ercjootrh@gmail.com)		
2.	PROTOCOLS SIGNED BY THE PRINCIPLE INVESTIGATORS		
3.	PROPOCOLS SIGNED BY THE SUPERVISORS (FOR STUDENTS)		
4.	SUPERVISORS EMAIL INDICATED (FOR STUDENTS)		
5.	PRESCRIBED FEES PAID		
6.	Ensure all relevant documents are attached:		
	(a) PRINCIPLES INVESTIGATOR'S/Co-PIs CURRICULUM VITAE		
	(b) Consent/ assent forms		
	(c) PROTOCOL'S budget		
	(d) Abstract		
	(e) Gantt Chart		
	(f) Contact of the PRINCIPLE INVESTIGATOR.		
	(g) Data capture tools where applicable.		
7.	SCHOOL OF GRADUATE STUDIES APPROVAL (STUDENTS)		
8.			

DATE 10.04.2025..... SIGN *Vin Tumbale*.....

APPROVED.....SIGN.....

Informed consent to participate in the research of the Waste in humanitarian Operations: Reduction and Minimisation (WORM) project

I have been requested to participate in the research identified above. I have received sufficient information about the research and processing of my personal data in the Privacy notice in writing (in print or electronic form) and have had the opportunity to ask questions and have my questions answered.

I understand that the participation in the research is voluntary. I am aware that I have the right to refuse to participate and the right to withdraw from the research permanently or for a temporary period at any time and without giving a reason. Withdrawal from the research will not result in any negative consequences to me. The information collected from or about me up to the point of my withdrawal may still be used in the research.

I agree that the interview with me will be recorded, and that photographs and videos be taken of me for the research's purpose. The recordings, photographs, and videos will be processed in such a way that I cannot be identified in them.

[In case the interview takes place as part of a workshop:]

I agree that videos or photographs of me taken during a WORM workshop are used in WORM communication and dissemination materials.

I understand that the personal data collected during the research will remain confidential and protected in accordance with relevant data protection legislations and research integrity. The information I have provided during the research can be used as anonymized statements in the publications. My identity as an individual research participant will not be disclosed in a scientific publication or any other research results to be published.

I agree that I can be contacted at a later stage for a further study or follow-up study.

I hereby give my voluntary consent to participate in this research.

The research participant's signature and name in block letters

(Consent can also be given electronically, for example, by email.)

Place and date

WORM researcher's name and contact details:

Virva Tuomala

Hanken School of Economics

The HUMLOG Institute P.O. Box 479 (Arkadiankatu 22) FI-00101 Helsinki Finland

virva.tuomala@hanken.fi

Concept Note: Travel to Kenya for Data Collection

Stay: May 26th, 2025 - June 12th, 2025

Reason: Data collection for the Waste Management in humanitarian Operations: Reduction and Minimisation (WORM) Project, a Horizon Europe funded project (Grant agreement ID 101135392) aimed at reducing the environmental impact of humanitarian operations. The project addresses waste management challenges in the field hospitals by designing guidelines and supporting actions for a circular economy.

Purpose: The primary purpose of this data collection trip is to document the medical waste management practices employed by Kenyan clinics, hospitals, and organizations in various operational contexts. By understanding these practices, the research aims to identify both strengths and areas for improvement in the management of medical waste.

As part of this visit, the researchers will also engage with waste pickers to understand how informal networks can support waste management in the country and contribute to a livelihood component.

Expected Outcomes:

1. Detailed records of medical waste management practices across various operational contexts in Kenya.
2. Highlighting effective strategies and methods currently in use that can be replicated or adapted in other settings.
3. Identifying areas where improvements are needed in the management of medical waste.
4. Contributing to the creation of guidelines for better waste management practices in the humanitarian sector.
5. Understanding the role of waste pickers and how informal networks can be integrated into formal waste management systems to enhance efficiency and support livelihoods.

worm

**Waste in humanitarian Operations:
Reduction and Minimisation**

Funded by the
European Union